

Test Evolution in Highly Configurable Systems vs. Single Systems

You are receiving this survey as our initial investigation identified you as either a test contributor of Highly Configurable System (HCS) or Single System (SS - traditional systems).

Highly Configurable System (HCS) are systems based on configuration options, such as `#ifdef` preprocessor directive in the C language. Single System (SS - traditional systems) are systems which do not rely on preprocessor directives or other mechanisms to allow configurations.

In this survey, we want to know your opinion regarding the differences related to testing evolution in HCS and SS. This survey should take about 10 minutes of your time.

Your participation is voluntary and confidential. You can withdraw at any time. We do not record any identifiable information.

This survey is conducted by a joint team of Computer Science researchers from the Federal University of Bahia (Brazil) and the University of California, Irvine (UCI).

We plan to include the results of this survey in a scientific publication. Should you be interested in being informed about the outcome of this study or any resulting publication, you will be provided an opportunity to indicate this at the end of the survey.

Please contact Jonatas Bastos (jonatasfbastos@ifba.edu.br) if you have any questions or comments related to the study.

Thank you!

ELECTRONIC CONSENT

Please select your choice below. Selecting the "yes" option below indicates that: i) you have read and understood the above information, ii) you voluntarily agree to participate, and iii) you are at least 18 years old. If you do not wish to participate in the research study, please decline participation by selecting "No".

*** Required**

Consent

1. I consent to participate in this research study *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

Demographics

2. Are you a professional software engineer paid by any company? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

3. How many years of development experience do you have (ex: 0, 1, 2, 3...10...)? *

4. What is your current country of residence? *

5. What is your highest educational qualification? *

Mark only one oval.

Less than high school

Graduated high school

Trade/technical school

Some college, no degree

Bachelor's degree

Advanced degree(Master's, Ph.D, M.D.)

Maintainability aspects

Based on your experience developing Highly Configurable Systems (HCS) and Single Systems (SS), choose the one that you agree the most.

- 6. Our investigation shows that at the beginning of a project in SS the number of test contributors is almost triple compared to HCS. Do you agree with this observation? *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

- 7. If you have any any additional comment, please add it here

- 8. Do you agree with the statement "Code complexity in HCS test is higher than SS" *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Agree
- Strongly agree
- Neutral

9. If you have any any additional comment, please add it here

10. The dependence of tests in HCS is higher than SS (the dependence of test code is measured by the coupling between the test code and the production code that is tested) *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Agree
- Strongly agree
- Neutral

11. If you have any any additional comment, please add it here

12. In our study, we found that code clones are more likely to be present in SS tests than HCS. *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Agree
- Strongly agree
- Neutral

13. If you have any any additional comment, please add it here

14. The variability present in HCS tests make it more difficult to maintain than SS tests.

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Agree
- Strongly agree
- Neutral

15. If you have any any additional comment, please add it here

16. Our results indicates that in HCS the average number of test lines modified in a month is higher than SS. Do you agree? *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree
- Neutral

17. If you have any any additional comment, please add it here

18. Do you have more experience as a contributor of *

Mark only one oval.

- Highly Configurable System (HCS) *Skip to question 19*
- Single System (SS) *Skip to question 26*

Test Contributors of HCS

19. We identified high values of the test contributors' workload in HCS (the amount of work by contributor in a project). Thus, do you agree that it is necessary more contributors only involved with tests activities? *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree
- Neutral

20. If you have any any additional comment, please add it here

21. In our study, we observed a high concentration of test work since 20% of the test contributors are responsible for 92% of the work performed in HCS. Do you believe that the high concentration of activities cause bottlenecks in development and communication? *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree
- Neutral

22. If you have any any additional comment, please add it here

23. Do you believe that the high workload negatively impact in the quality of tests? *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree
- Neutral

24. If you have any any additional comment, please add it here

25. Based on your experience, what are the main challenges related to testing in HCS?

Skip to question 32

Test Contributors of SS

26. We identified high values of test contributors' workload in SS (the amount of work done by contributors in a project). Do you think it is necessary to have more contributors involved with only testing activities to reduce the workload? *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

27. If you have any any additional comment, please add it here

28. In our study, we observed a high concentration of test work as 20% of the test contributors are responsible for 85% of the work performed in SS. Do you believe that a high concentration of activity causes bottlenecks in development and communication? *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

29. Do you believe that high workload negatively impacts the quality of tests? *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

30. If you have any any additional comment, please add it here

31. Based on your experience, what are the main challenges related to test development in SS?

Email Information (optional)

32. Please, provide your email if you would like to receive a copy of our study:

Google Forms